

A process for producing 3-quinuclidinone hydrochloride by oxidation of unwanted isomer 3-S-quinuclidinol

Ramadas Chavakula*, Mutyala Narayana Rao and Chennupati Srinivasa Rao

Tyche Industries Limited, H. No : C-21/A, Road No. 9, Film Nagar, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad-500 033, India

E-mail : das.krishnac@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 03 April 2012, revised 07 April 2012, accepted 18 April 2012

Abstract : An industrially efficient method was developed synthetic process for the preparation of 3-quinuclidinone HCl by recycling of 3-S-quinuclidinol in one step sequence of oxidation process. Oxidation of secondary alcohol of 3-S-quinuclidinol which utilises complexes of a sulfide such as dimethyl sulfide with *N*-chlorosuccinimide to give target compound in high yield.

Keywords : 3-S-Quinuclidinol, NCS, dimethyl sulfide, oxidation and reduction, racemic mixture.

Introduction

3-*R*-Quinuclidinol (1) can be obtained by kinetic resolution of racemic mixtures of *R*- and *S*-3-quinuclidinol(IV). 3-*R*-Quinuclidinol (*R*-1-azabicyclo[2,2,2]octan-3-ol) (1) is used as a building block in the synthesis of muscarine M1 and M3 agonists as well as for muscarine M3 antagonists. See for example the recent review by Broadley and Kelly¹ concerning muscarinic receptor agonist and antagonist. Talsaclidinfumarate (WAL 2014 FU)²⁻⁴, cevimeline HCl^{5,6} and YM 905⁷ are all examples of products where 3-*R*-quinuclidinol (1) constitutes an integral part of the molecular entity. These products have shown potential in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease, sjogren syndrome, and urinary incontinence, respectively. 3-*R*-Quinuclidinol (1) constitutes therefore a highly valuable building block for the synthetic production of several important pharmaceutical chemicals. Thus, in this context, need to reduce cost of process by recycling 3-*S*-quinuclidinol (2). Process for recycling of 3-*S*-quinuclidinol by using TEMPO (2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidin-1-oxyl) radical and molecular chlorine and have been described⁸. All these methods commonly require expensive reagents, low temperatures and tedious procedures, thus we report here an improved reproducible process and is amenable to scale up. This invention provides a simple and indus-

trially viable process for the synthesis of 3-quinuclidinone-III from 3-*S*-quinuclidinol (2). The chemical literature reports several methods to be generally applicable for oxidizing secondary alcohols into their corresponding ketones⁹. We now report the preparation of 3-quinuclidinone from 3-*S*-quinuclidinol by the Corey-Kim oxidation^{10,11}. Oxidation of 3-*S*-quinuclidinol is a process which is operationally simple, highly selective, and efficient in plant scale. The oxidation reaction is given in Scheme 1.

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ADVANCE 400 MHz spectrometer using MeOD as solvent and SiMe₄ as internal standard.

Preparation of 3-quinuclidinone hydrochloride (3a) :

To a solution of 3-*S*-quinuclidinol (50 g, 0.3937 mol) in chloroform (1 L) at -10 °C to -15 °C, dimethyl sulfide (24.5 g, 0.394 mol) and TEA (110 g, 1.089 mol) were added in a single lot under argon and stirred for 15-30 min. *N*-Chlorosuccinamide (160 g, 1.2 mol) was added lot wise over 1 h while maintaining the internal temperature at -10 °C to -15 °C. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 10 °C to -15 °C. Completion of reaction was monitored by Gas Chromatography (GC). After

Scheme 1

completion of reaction, dilute sodium hydroxide solution (150 g 1 L of water) was added slowly at temperature less than $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After the addition, the mixture was warmed to $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and stirred for 1 h at $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The aqueous and organic layers were separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with chloroform ($200\text{ ml} \times 3$). The organic layer was distilled off completely under vacuum. To the residue charged isopropyl alcohol 200 ml and stirred for 15 min. Cool to $10\text{--}15^{\circ}$ and slowly added IPA. HCl (50 ml) to get pH (1–2). Stirred for 1 h. Filtered the reaction mass and washed with isopropyl alcohol (50 ml). Weight 50 g (79%).

Quinuclidinone base ^1H NMR (MeOD) : δ 3.38–2.82 (5H, m), 2.46–1.62 (6H, m).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Tyche Industries Limited for financial assistance.

References

1. K. J. Broadley and D. R. Kelly, *Molecules*, 2001, **6**, 142.
2. *Drugs Future*, 1998, **24**, 79.
3. G. Roman, *Drugs Today*, 2000, **36**, 641.
4. *Drugs Future*, 2000, **26**, 61.
5. M. F. Siggiqui and A. I. Levey, *Drugs Future*, 1999, **24**, 417.
6. L. A. Sorbera and I. Castaner, *Drugs Future*, 2000, **25**, 558.
7. N. Mealy and J. Castaner, *Drugs Future*, 1999, **24**, 871.
8. H. R. Bjorsvik, L. Liguori, F. Costantino and F. Minisci, *Organic Process Research & Development*, 2002, **6**, 197.
9. A. H. Haines, "Methods for the oxidation of organic compounds : alcohols, alcohol derivatives, alkyl halides, nitroalkanes, alkyl azides, carbonyl compounds, hydroxyarenes and aminoarenes. Best synthetic methods", Academic Press, London, 1988, pp. 1-467.
10. E. J. Corey and C. U. Kim, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 7586.
11. E. J. Corey and C. U. Kim, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1973, **38**, 1233.